

ACADEMIC PLAGIARISM IS A PROBLEM IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT: *The aim of this study is to explore some of the difficulties and challenges that ESL learners experience in academic writing. The study seeks to answer the research question, “What challenges do ESL learners encounter in Academic writing?”, “What factors can expose learners to plagiarism?” and “How to deal with these Academic writing problems related to plagiarism?”. The goal is to analyze the data collected from a variety of articles regarding the topic, find relevant references or contradictory viewpoints and come to valid conclusions.*

KEYWORDS: *English language, academic writing, learning, challenges, academic plagiarism, essay checking service.*

INTRODUCTION

Plagiarism at university is a form of cheating and is a serious academic offence. It arises from work submitted that is not the student's own. This includes students taking text and ideas from other sources without adequate or appropriate referencing, with poor paraphrasing and containing blatant copying. The most common forms of plagiarism are copying, collusion, fabrication and misrepresentation. Far more serious is when students commission work and buy essays.

MAIN BODY

First, plagiarism signifies copying others' work by not mentioning the authors and a lack of rewording. In spite of the fact that the Turnitin plagiarism software are applied by academic institutions in order to find out whether the assignment is copied

or not, the service of a custom essay writing which costs a certain amount of money is common and widely used by students. Such services even make use of adverts online or around university places so as to promote their work, offering ranging from essays to doctoral thesis. They also ensure that their work can be created with fully plagiarism free and no-one can identify it from originality. The reason why students are tapping into such online services is hardly explainable. In general, the reason might be insufficient time or a number of deadlines (Rogerson,2014). It is also important to note that using ‘custom essay writing service’ is becoming more popular among international students as universities do not pay attention to students’ level of the language. This process may have a negative impact on the evaluation for students’ assignments, bring about unfairness which in turn leads to diminishing academic places reputation. Moreover, proving that a student has applied this service is a daunting task and students have excuses to say that they have done the assignment themselves. The final point is that in order to abolish such writing services, it is crucial to introduce a law. In my opinion, this article clearly describes about the current issue for universities which have difficulty assessing the students’ real knowledge because of the online services. However, there are also weak points about this article in which the real reasons are not fully explained by the author. I think for this aspect a further research or investigation should be conducted. In the article, I feel that the central point and threat is that there has been a significant rise in the application of this service among students. This is a warning for us, in other words, in the future graduates who have implemented this tool during their academic career are not capable of being qualified, being professional at their sphere or competing in the job market owing to lack of knowledge and researching.

There is no one specific explanation for students using these services. Generally, poor time management and multiple deadlines are considered the main reasons (Rogerson, 2014). There is also the pressure of such a high investment and fear of failing (Medway et al., 2018). Of course, it is also seen as an easier option to obtain a higher grade, especially when there seems to be a legal vagueness over the use of

writing mills. Research by Mostrous & Kenber, (2016) suggests that international students are four-times more likely to use these than native students. The evidence suggests key factors are differing cultural interpretations on what is considered cheating and/or not being able to meet the academic conventions of analytical or critical evaluation. A key point here is that many universities are accepting international students with lower English abilities and thus language competence is significant reason to have someone else write your essay.

I completely agree that this writing service can influence on their academic performance and certainly future career. I feel that without obtaining proper knowledge and qualification with the help of such kind of online services after graduating from the university, it is impossible for them to find their way and position in the workplaces. Because, the communities or corporations do not need such employees who have not investigated in their domain sufficiently. I am also of the opinion that in order to stop such services, we need legislation. Any student who has used while preparing his or her academic assignment ought to be punished harshly which might potentially inhibit other students from applying this service.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I completely agree that this writing service can influence on their academic performance and certainly future career. I feel that without obtaining proper knowledge and qualification with the help of such kind of online services after graduating from the university, it is impossible for them to find their way and position in the workplaces. Because, the communities or corporations do not need such employees who have not investigated in their domain sufficiently. I am also of the opinion that in order to stop such services, we need legislation. Any student who has used while preparing his or her academic assignment ought to be punished harshly which might potentially inhibit other students from applying this service.

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